

MONITORING THE MANUFACTURING PROCESS AND THE MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF A FULL-SIZED ALL CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE AIRCRAFT TAILCONE ASSEMBLY USING EMBEDDED FIBRE OPTIC SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

Optical fibre sensors were embedded into carbon-fibre-reinforced-preform (CFRP) during the industrial manufacturing of a full-sized, one-piece tailcone for a regional jet aircraft, and monitored the production process and thereafter the post-fabrication mechanical loading tests. The carbon fibre preform was laid onto a specially made tailcone-shaped tooling using an automated industrial robotic system while the optical fibres were hand-laid to ensure precise positioning and orientation of the sensors. The tailcone preform was sealed in vacuum bags, infused with resin and subsequently cured in a large industrial oven. The infusion of resin into the preform was monitored successfully by optical fibre Fresnel sensors via measurement of the refractive index-dependent attenuation of the reflected light signal. The curing process was monitored via the chemical cure reaction-dependent change in refractive index of the resin using optical fibre Fresnel sensors, and via the development of strain using optical fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors fabricated in single mode (SM) and in high linearly birefringent (HiBi) fibres. The through-thickness transverse strain measured by the HiBi FBG sensors was able to detect material shrinkage early, while the longitudinal strain measured by the SM FBG sensors detected material shrinkage ~115 minutes later, during the cure process that was performed over a duration of 240 minutes. The measured average through-thickness transverse strain and the average longitudinal strain corresponding to material shrinkage were ~1440 $\mu\epsilon$ and ~160 $\mu\epsilon$, respectively. The embedded FBG sensors were subsequently used to monitor structural strains which were in good agreement with measurements from surface-bonded resistance foil strain gauge (RFSG) rosette sensors, when the interior of the tailcone was subjected to vacuum pressure loadings after manufacture. Maximum longitudinal strains measured by the embedded SM FBG and surface-bonded RFSG sensors were 274 $\mu\epsilon$ and 178 $\mu\epsilon$, respectively, at -51 mbar of the applied vacuum pressure. In-plane transverse and circumferential strains, oriented collinearly and measured by HiBi FBG and RFSG sensors respectively, were in good agreement, qualitatively.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are primarily lightweight and they have a large strength to weight ratio, making them important for energy conservation in a range of applications, including aerospace. The manufacturing processes of composite components are often complex and on-line monitoring procedures become vital for quality control. The process of laying-up the preform, filling the preform with resin and the subsequent resin curing process have direct influence on the quality of the final composite part. Small scale laboratory monitoring of these processes are performed using conventional non-optical methods [1] such as dielectric [2, 3] and ultrasonic sensors [4] for resin flow, void fraction and degree of cure and pressure sensors for resin flow [5]. These sensors are usually confined to laboratory use as they are either un-embeddable or relatively large for embedding into components for real life applications.

Quality control in composites manufacturing can be implemented by the use of embedded sensors that are capable of providing real-time monitoring. Optical fibre sensors are well suited to this application because they have many appropriate characteristics, including their small diameter, which is typically 40-125 μm . Resin infusion and cure can be measured efficiently by monitoring the refractive index-dependent changes in the Fresnel reflections from a cleaved fibre end [6-9]. Optical fibre interferometers, such as extrinsic Fabry-Perot interferometers, have been used to monitor the development of internal strains during a curing composite [10]. The infusion, flow and cure of resin can be monitored using optical fibre grating sensors such as fibre Bragg grating (FBG), tilted fibre Bragg grating (TFBG), and long period grating (LPG) sensors [6, 11]. Grating sensors are versatile as they can be configured to perform multiple-parameter sensing.

This work demonstrated the industrial-scale manufacturing of a full-scale, one-piece aircraft tailcone assembly from wholly composite material, while being monitored using embedded optical fibre sensors fabricated in single mode (SM) and high linearly birefringent (HiBi) optical fibre. Multiplexed optical Fresnel, SM FBG and HiBi FBG sensors were embedded to monitor the infusion of resin, the cure of resin and the development of longitudinal and transverse strains. The embedded grating sensors, along with surface-mounted resistance foil strain gauge (RFSG) rosettes, were later used to monitor structural strains in subsequent post-fabrication mechanical tests.

2 PREFORM AND SENSOR LAY-UP

A total of 7 plies of dry carbon fibre were laid onto the main body or standard structure area shown in figure 1a using an automated dry fibre placement (ADFP) set-up implemented by an industrial robotic system [12]. Optical fibre sensors were embedded in the standard structure area in 4 zones, that is, F1-F4 (Fig. 1b). The sensors were hand laid after the first 3 plies of carbon fibre had been placed, after which 4 more plies were added (Fig. 2). Each of the zones F1-F4 consisted of three embedded polyimide-coated optical fibres; one single-mode (SM) fibre with a Fresnel sensor at its distal end, one SM fibre containing 5 equal-spaced fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors, and one high linearly birefringent (HiBi) fibre containing 5 equal-spaced FBG sensors (Fig. 1). The FBG sensors along the length of the optical fibres, each with different centre wavelength, are marked from S1-S5 (Fig. 1). Each section of the optical fibre containing an FBG sensor, 2 mm long, was stripped before fabrication and was not recoated. The distal end of each optical fibre containing the SM FBG sensors was also used as a Fresnel sensor.

The ADFP system was paused after laying-up the first 3 plies of fabric to allow for the hand-laying of the optical fibre sensors before the ADFP process was resumed to complete the lay-up of an additional 4 plies. Hand-laying of the sensors was necessary to guarantee precise location of the sensors in the tailcone and for precise orienting of the HiBi FBG polarisation Eigen axes with the principal directions (in-plane and out-of-plane) of the tailcone. Such precise orientation was necessary to allow the HiBi FBG sensors to be configured to measure transverse strains that are in-plane or out-of-plane [13, 14] of the tailcone while the measurements from the SM FBG sensors were interpreted as longitudinal strain. The effects of the longitudinal strain on the HiBi FBG signals is removed by the signal processing described in [13, 14], while the measurements from the thermocouple sensors were used to compensate for the temperature effects in the HiBi FBG and SM FBG signals.

The tailcone preform was reinforced in the through-thickness direction, after lay-up, by means of tufting at the feet of the stringers. (The authors have also performed on-line monitoring of the strains in the needle during the tufting process using multiplexed SM FBG sensors which were surface-bonded to the needle [9, 15]).

Figure 1: (a) 3D drawing of the tailcone and (b) Rear view of the tailcone exterior showing optical fibre sensor locations S1 to S5 within each of the zones F1 to F4 of the tailcone. The length and diameter of the tailcone is ~ 2.5 m and ~ 1.6 m, respectively.

3 INFUSION AND CURE

Figure 2 shows the tailcone preform which was placed in an oven after it was installed with vacuum bags and made ready for the infusion of resin and the subsequent cure process. The infusion and cure accessories were located outside the oven and so was the instrumentation for interrogating the optical sensors. The resin inlet was located at the bottom of the tailcone which was placed upright in the oven with the exhaust-end located at the top.

Figure 2: Tailcone preform sealed within vacuum bags and fixed upright in the oven ready for resin infusion and cure processes.

3.1 Fresnel sensor

A cleaved end of an optical fibre, which was polyimide coated, was used as a Fresnel sensing element (Fig. 3a). Light propagating in the core of the fibre will simultaneously reflect and transmit partially at the fibre-end interface with the surrounding medium. The amount of the reflected light is a function of the effective refractive index of the fibre mode for the light propagating in it and that of the

surrounding medium, as shown by figure 3b. An accurate measurement of the refractive index of the surrounding medium can be obtained by making use of another cleaved fibre end located in the same temperature environment as the sensing fibre but exposed to air, which is required to provide a reference signal for the normalisation of the reflected intensities. The Fresnel equation [6] is used to determine the required refractive index of the surrounding medium.

A Fresnel sensor interrogator was configured with spatially multiplexed sensor elements to measure simultaneously refractive index at 8 different locations and to monitor the air reference. The intensity of a broadband light source was modulated at 1 kHz before it was coupled to the fibres containing the Fresnel sensors, and the reflected signals were demodulated at the same frequency by a data acquisition system that was based on lock-in amplifiers (NI PXI—4462), which enhanced the signal to noise ratio. The instrument was used to monitor the infusion of the resin, and subsequently to monitor the change in refractive index of the resin during the cure cycle. The relationship between refractive index and degree of cure had been established by monitoring the refractive index and the heat of reaction of a sample of curing resin, which were measured by the Fresnel sensor and the differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) [16, 17] respectively, in separate characterisation experiments performed under identical conditions. The drastic attenuation in the reflected signal of the Fresnel sensor was used to indicate the arrival of resin at the sensor. Subsequently, as the resin cured, the reflected signal intensity changed as the refractive index of the resin changed, which was exploited as a phenomenological measurement of the degree of cure.

Figure 3. Optical fibre Fresnel sensor showing (a) sensing principle and (b) plot of reflectivity as a function of external refractive index, calculated assuming that the effective index of the fibre mode for the light propagating through the optical fibre is 1.45.

Figure 4a shows that Fresnel sensor-1, embedded midway along the length of the tailcone in zone-F3, detected the arrival of the resin 24 minutes after the infusion process was started, which was before the resin was detected 1.5 minutes later by Fresnel sensor-2, located closest to the exhaust-end of the tailcone in zone-F1. The arrival of the resin at the middle of the tailcone before the exhaust end was expected, as the resin inlet was located at the bottom of the tailcone. The Fresnel sensor signals in figure 4a were noisy, early in the curing phase, and for this reason they were not used to determine the refractive index change caused by the cure reaction. The signal from the Fresnel sensor is susceptible to the movement and bending of the sensor element within the preform, which may account for the noise. Figure 4b shows the result of a calibration of the same neat resin system by using a temperature-modulated DSC [17] experiment which was plotted together with a refractive index measurement from a Fresnel sensor, showing good correlation between the two measurements.

Figure 4: (a) Resin infusion into tailcone detected by 2 Fresnel sensors, one located midway (Fresnel sensor-1) along the length of tailcone showing resin arrival at 24 minutes and the other (Fresnel sensor-2) closet to the exhaust end showing resin arrival at 25.5 minutes (b) Correlation of the Fresnel sensor refractive index measurement with the degree of cure measured by the DSC experiment for a neat resin.

3.2 SM FBG and HiBi FBG sensors

The infusion of RTM 6 resin into the tailcone was followed by the curing process which was monitored simultaneously by the embedded HiBi FBG and SM FBG sensors that detected transverse and longitudinal strains, respectively, developed during the chemical cure reaction. The wavelength spectrum of light reflected by an SM FBG sensor is characterised by a single peak of narrow wavelength band (~ 0.2 nm), while the reflection from a HiBi FBG sensor exhibits two peaks with a wavelength separation of ~ 0.3 nm [13, 14]. The HiBi FBG peaks lay in the two orthogonal polarisation Eigen axes of the fibre [13, 14]. The SM FBG and HiBi FBG sensors were interrogated simultaneously using separate instrumentation. A laser source (Santec, HSL 2000) that scanned a 110-nm wavelength bandwidth centred at 1318 nm at a rate of 20 kHz was configured around single mode optical fibre components for interrogating the SM FBG sensors. The HiBi FBG sensors were interrogated by a laser source with a 49 nm bandwidth centred at 1286 nm and a scan rate of 2.5 kHz that was configured with HiBi optical fibre components. Data capture from the two interrogation systems was performed at a rate of 2.5 kHz. The polarisation Eigen axes of the HiBi FBG sensors were aligned with the in-plane and out-of-plane directions of the tailcone, making it possible to monitor the out-of-plane transverse strains developed during the curing process [13] as discussed in section 2. All the SM and HiBi optical fibres were embedded such that they were oriented with the

long axis of the tailcone. Figure 5 shows the transverse and longitudinal strains measured by FBG sensors embedded at sensor position S4 in zone-F1 of the tailcone, monitored during the curing process. The longitudinal strain in figure 5 shows the material exhibited shrinkage (i.e. decrease in strain) relatively late, ~115 minutes after the shrinkage was detected by the transverse strain, when the cure was performed over 240 minutes. The longitudinal strain measurements, therefore, most likely underestimated the material expansion and material shrinkage in the tailcone while overestimating the residual strain.

The out-of-plane transverse strains corresponding to material expansion, material shrinkage and residual strain, are $595 \mu\epsilon$, $1615 \mu\epsilon$ and $-1020 \mu\epsilon$ respectively (Fig. 5a), while the longitudinal strains corresponding to material expansion, material shrinkage and residual strain are $454 \mu\epsilon$, $179 \mu\epsilon$ and $275 \mu\epsilon$ respectively (Fig. 5b). The magnitudes of the transverse strains measured in different zones of the tailcone were comparable, as were the magnitudes of the longitudinal strains monitored in the different zones. The extent of the cure process in the different zones of the tailcone is therefore consistent. The measured out-of-plane strain averages of the material expansion, material shrinkage and residual strains were $\sim 300 \mu\epsilon$, $\sim 1440 \mu\epsilon$ and $\sim 1100 \mu\epsilon$ respectively, while the corresponding longitudinal strain averages were $\sim 560 \mu\epsilon$, $\sim 160 \mu\epsilon$ and $\sim 410 \mu\epsilon$, respectively.

Figure 5: Strain developed in the tailcone in Zone-F1 at sensor position S4 during the curing process (a) out-of-plane transverse strain measured by an embedded HiBi FBG and (b) longitudinal strain measured by an embedded SM FBG.

4 STRUCTURAL TESTS

The embedded FBG sensors, which were used earlier in monitoring the manufacturing processes of the tailcone, were used simultaneously with surfaced-bonded resistance foil strain gauge (RFSG) rosette sensors in monitoring structural strains during post-fabrication vacuum pressure load tests. The RFSG rosette measured longitudinal, shear and circumferential strains at each sensor location (Fig. 6). Figure 6 describes the strain components which were measured by the FBG and RFSG sensors. Longitudinal strain (Fig. 6) was measured by both the embedded SM FBG and the RFSG rosette and compared together. The embedded HiBi FBG was configured to monitor an in-plane transverse strain [15] which was compared to the circumferential strain that was measured by the surface-bonded RFSG rosette, as the two strains were oriented in the same direction (Fig. 6). The interior of the tailcone was subjected to vacuum pressure loads after the interior walls were lined with vacuum bags and the window and door areas were sealed with thin aluminium foil.

Figure 6: Strain components measured by the embedded FBG (green arrows) and surface-mounted RFSG (blue arrows) rosette.

Figure 7 describes the structural strains monitored in zone-F1 of the tailcone by the embedded FBG and surface-bonded RFSG rosette sensors when vacuum pressure loads were applied to the tailcone interior. The in-plane transverse strain and the circumferential strain monitored by the embedded HiBi FBG and the surface-mounted RFSG rosette respectively, have the same trend (Fig. 7a). The in-plane transverse strain is significantly larger than the circumferential strain. Figure 7a shows a maximum in-plane transverse strain and circumferential strain of $\sim 173 \mu\epsilon$ and $\sim 74 \mu\epsilon$, respectively, for a maximum vacuum pressure of -51 mbar . The embedded SM FBG and RFSG rosette sensors monitored longitudinal strains which were in close agreement, both in magnitude and trend (Fig. 7b). The maximum longitudinal strain measured was $\sim 70 \mu\epsilon$ for a maximum vacuum pressure of -51 mbar (Fig. 7b).

Figure 7: (a) Circumferential and in-plane transverse strains measured by a surface-bonded RFSG and an embedded HiBi FBG, respectively and (b) longitudinal strains measured by a surface-bonded RFSG and an embedded SM FBG, during vacuum pressure loading in the interior of the tailcone. The sensors are located in zone-F1 of the tailcone.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The industrial manufacturing processes of a large, one-piece, full-scale and all-composite-material airplane tailcone was monitored successfully with embedded optical fibre sensors, from carbon-fibre preform lay-up through production to post-fabrication load tests. The infusion of resin into the tailcone preform was monitored successfully using multiplexed Fresnel sensors that were embedded in different locations. The developments of longitudinal and transverse strains in the tailcone were respectively monitored by the embedded SM FBG and HiBi FBG sensors simultaneously, during the curing resin subsequently after infusion. The magnitudes of the transverse strains measured in different zones of the tailcone were comparable and so were the magnitudes of the longitudinal strains monitored in the different zones. The extent of the cure process in the different zones of the tailcone was therefore consistent. The measured longitudinal strain exhibited material shrinkage relatively late,

compared to transverse strain which allowed the detection of the shrinkage ~115 minutes earlier, during the cure process.

The tailcone was later subjected to vacuum pressure loadings after manufacture, with the resulting structural strains being monitored simultaneously by the same embedded FBG sensors together with surface-bonded RFSG rosettes. Longitudinal strains monitored by both the embedded SM FBG and RFSG sensors were in close agreement. The RFSG sensors measured circumferential strains, which were in good agreement, qualitatively, with the in-plane transverse strains monitored by the embedded HiBi FBG sensors. The magnitude of the strains was significantly different, with the in-plane transverse strains larger than the circumferential strains.

This work demonstrated the significance of optical fibre sensors, which are embedded within fibre-reinforced composites, in providing an entire monitoring solution to the composite manufacturing processes.

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